
Polydopamine may be easily functionalized with a range of nanomaterials for synergistic cancer therapy, in addition to its exceptional photothermal effects

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Abstract: Recent breakthroughs in photothermal treatment coupled with complex therapies such as gene therapy, radiation, and especially immunotherapy were highlighted. Due to their exceptional biocompatibility, degradability, low toxicity and high photothermal conversion efficiency, facile oxidative self-polymerization of dopamine can create PDA and serve as an excellent nanocarrier or photothermal cancer treatment agent. Due to its high adhesive capacity, PDA may be easily functionalized with a range of nanomaterials for synergistic cancer therapy, in addition to its exceptional photothermal effects. Although PDA-based multifunctional nanoplateforms have gained interest for synergistic cancer therapy, such as chemo-photothermal treatment and photodynamic-photothermal treatment, discovering novel uses for PDA remains tough. First, despite its easy and mild process of synthesis, large-scale synthesis with uniform size and thickness is challenging owing to the absence of consistent quality control standards. Second, due to the strong adhesive properties of PDA, multifunctional nanoplateforms are prone to aggregating in a solution. Third, to improve PDA's clinical application, its safety should be fully researched. Before being deployed in clinical settings, PDA-based multifunctional systems need additional research. A PDA-based multifunctional platform for better synergistic cancer treatment is a forward-looking strategy. Besides immunotherapy, in recent years, the integration of cancer diagnosis and treatment has gained a lot of publicity. Polyphenols have been proven to suppress tumor development and interact with metals such as Fe³⁺, Pt⁴⁺, Cu²⁺, etc (MPNs). MPNs are biocompatible, functional, pH-responsive and can escape endosomes. PDA has the potential to develop MPNs with contrasting magnetic resonance agents like gadolinium due to the enormous quantity of catechol groups on its surface, allowing magnetic resonance imaging. Polyphenols also have tumor-inhibiting effects, and PDA's photothermal activity can ablate tumors. Consequently, PDA-based MPNs might be a promising way to integrate diagnosis and treatment. Moreover, polydopamine can crosslink acrylamide and other polymers to form anticancer and antibacterial hydrogels. Increasing the stickiness of polydopamine hydrogels is now underway, paving the path for self-adhesive bioelectronics hydrogels. Bioelectron self-adhesion and other capabilities such as self-healing, transparency, and bacterio-toxicity may be supplied to polydopamine hydrogels by altering phenolquinone's redox process. A prospective future trend is using self-adhesive polydopamine hydrogels with current bioelectronic materials. We think that polydopamine hydrogels will eventually advance from skin patches to implantable integrated bioelectronics.

1. Introduction

Despite advances in knowledge, cancer continues to be the leading cause of mortality. In 2019, 762 450 new cancer cases and 606 880 cancer deaths are expected in the United States.

1 and 2 Conventional cancer treatments, such as surgery, irradiation, and chemotherapy, are known to have a number of drawbacks, including high toxicity and a lack of selectivity. Controlled drug delivery systems are thought to be advantageous in cancer treatments because they are more effective and have fewer adverse effects. (3), (4) Due to its inherent advantages, such as good biocompatibility, degradability, low toxicity, ease of functionalization, and synthesis, PDA has been the focus of considerable scientific attention since Lee and co-workers first reported on the preparation of polydopamine (PDA) via simple oxidative self-polymerization of dopamine in 2007. (6-9) PDA has been used in biological applications, including medication delivery, bioimaging, and tissue engineering biosensing. (10-12) PDA has a unique structure that allows it to load anticancer medications (such as doxorubicin (DOX)) through stacking or hydrogen bonding interactions, with loading rates as high as 91%. Surprisingly, in addition to its great capacity to adsorb pharmaceuticals, PDA is also efficient in releasing pharmaceuticals by internal stimulation (hydrogen peroxide) or external stimulation (near-infrared (NIR) irradiation), lowering chemotherapy drug toxicity. (13-15) PDA can also operate as a photothermal agent, producing enough heat to ablate cancer cells when bombarded with 808 nm NIR light, according to its 40% light-to-heat conversion efficiency. PDA has a higher photothermal conversion effect and better biocompatibility than other photothermal materials such as carbon or copper-based nanomaterials and gold nanoparticles. (16-20)

Monotherapy has been shown to have many limitations owing to tumor heterogeneity and drug resistance, with synergistic treatments being more beneficial for cancer treatment. (21) PDA films have better adhesion due to the huge number of catechol and amine groups, allowing them to cling to a range of material surfaces, including gold nanoparticles, iron oxide, silica, and polylactic-co-glycolic acid (PLGA). As a result, dopamine polymerization has been used to functionalize practically every type of nanomaterial. More importantly, a layer of PDA confers highly desirable properties on nanomaterials, such as the ability to be loaded with drugs for controlled release, excellent photothermal conversion efficiency, and biocompatibility, facilitating the development of multifunctional drug delivery systems for combined treatment by combining photothermal therapy (PTT) or chemotherapy with other treatments. (22-25) The catechol and amino groups on PDA also serve as a bridge for further alteration. For example, using its amine and thiol groups, PDA can function as a link to deliver tumor-targeting ligands via a Michael addition or Schiff reaction, allowing nanoparticles to become concentrated at the tumor location. (26-28)

Researchers have created a variety of PDA-based multifunctional platforms for synergistic cancer treatment based on these features. PDA-based drug delivery systems for tumor-targeted and controlled-release medicines were evaluated by Wang et al. (29) in 2018. Ambekar et al. (30) described the production of polydopamine-based nanocarriers and the application of PDA-based nanoparticles in cancer combination therapy, such as chemotherapy/PTT therapy and photodynamic/PTT therapy, in 2019.

Recent studies have either not discussed PDA's significance in advanced therapies, such as gene therapy, radiation, biotherapy, or immunotherapy, or are out of date and do not explain the current research, since possible uses of PDA have expanded rapidly. We've looked at PDA as a bridge to targeted treatment for a range of tumor-specific drug delivery applications in this article. Furthermore, PDA nanoparticles (NPs) and PDA-based multifunctional platforms have been developed for usage alone and in combination with cancer treatments, including immunotherapy.

2. PDA as a Transitional Agent for Tumor-Targeting Ligands

Because of their increased permeability and retention, nano drug delivery systems (DDs) have been widely employed in cancer treatments. Drug retention time around tumors is increased by DDs, which improves bioavailability and stability. (31) and (32) DDs are often modified with various targeting ligands in order to improve targeting and tumoral uptake capabilities. However, because most nanomaterials lack reactive functional groups, they must be activated with coupling agents or reactive linkers before going through a time-consuming and inefficient purification process. (33) PDA is used to functionalize nanomaterials to make synthesis easier and more efficient. Using a simple and moderate synthesis technique, PDA may build a water-insoluble polymer layer on practically any material surface. (34) The PDA layer can be utilized as a bridge to incorporate ligand molecules containing amines or thiols due to the abundance of catechol and amino groups. In this section, we'll look at how PDA may be used to connect targeting agents like small molecules (Folic acid), nucleic acid aptamers (AS1411), and peptides to multifunctional nanoparticles.

2.1 Small Molecules

Small molecule targeted ligands have a high affinity for the folate receptor, which is overexpressed in cancer cells. Folic acid (FA), a water-soluble B vitamin that is stable and causes low immunogenicity, has a high affinity for the folate receptor, which is overexpressed in cancer cells. (35) Despite the fact that FA has been shown to be useful in targeting tumor locations, attaching FA to the surface of nanoparticles has proven difficult. Cheng et al. (37) coated mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) with a PDA coating and subsequently treated them with FA. The following were the exact synthetic steps: To coat the MSNs, dopamine was initially self-polymerized into polydopamine under mild alkaline circumstances. Second, by Michael's addition, thiol-modified folic acid ligands (HS-PEG-FA) were linked to the surface of the PDA-coated MSNs.

PDA was effectively coated on the surface of MSNs and subsequently conjugated with PEG-FA, as evidenced by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. MSNs@PDA-PEG-FA were taken up and dispersed more broadly inside tumor tissues than MSNs-DOX@PDA-PEG in a HeLa cell uptake and targeting experiment, showing that it demonstrated considerably better tumor targeting and produced enhanced endocytosis. Similarly, for targeted therapy, a new nanocapsule was created by coating drug-loaded black phosphorus nanosheets with PDA and then introducing the targeting polymer HS-PEG-FA. (38) Nanocapsules were injected into tumor-bearing nude mice to evaluate in vivo biodistribution. When compared to free DOX and BP-DOX@PDA-PEG groups, DOX-loaded BP@PDA-PEG-FA showed significant accumulation efficacy at tumor locations after 3 hours.

Nie et al. (39) discovered that PDA may be connected to amino-poly (ethylene glycol)-folic acid in addition to HS-PEG-FA. They developed a PDA-coated PLGA nanocarrier, which they subsequently functionalized with NH₂-PEG-FA and bortezomib (BTZ). The findings showed that NH₂-PEG-FA ligands were integrated into the PDA layer and played a role in actively targeting the tumor, resulting in a more effective breast cancer therapeutic effect. In addition, surface-modified PDA was used to bind the small molecule targeting ligand galactosamine onto nanocarriers. To summarize, PDA may be used to introduce small molecule ligands for drug delivery that are adorned with amine or thiol groups, resulting in tailored cancer treatment.

Aptamers

Nucleolin is a protein that is overexpressed in cancer cells like MCF-7 breast cancer cells and HeLa cervical cancer cells, among others. AS1411, a DNA aptamer that binds to nucleolin selectively, is an effective targeting ligand for monitoring cancer cells. (40) AS1411 with an amine (NH₂-) or thiol (SH-) termination can connect to the surface of polydopamine for effective targeting action, just as the folic acid ligand. An anti-miR-155 vector was recently produced using mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs), polydopamine, and the AS1411 aptamer. (41) MSNs–NH₂ and anti-miR-155 were mixed at 4 °C for 2 hours before being coated with polydopamine via covalent and noncovalent interactions. Finally, the SH-AS1411 aptamer was covalently conjugated onto the PDA film after 3 hours of stirring in the dark at room temperature. As previously stated, the overall system's synthesis was basic and modest. The nanoparticles demonstrated high active targeting capability and efficiently eradicated tumors in both in vivo and in vitro experiments. (42)

2.3 Targeting Peptides

2.3.1 Arginine-Glycine-Aspartate-Cysteine (RGDC)

RGDC (arginine-glycine-aspartate-cysteine) is a small molecule peptide that binds to the overexpressed α_3 integrin on the surface of tumor cells via RGD. (43) RGDC was mounted on the surface of the PDA to form a composite nanoplatform (PDA–RGD), and DOX was loaded through stacking and hydrogen bond interactions to give the PDA more targeting capacity. (44) PDA was used as a photothermal agent in this nanoplatform, and it had outstanding photoacoustic (PA) contrast qualities. The results showed that PDA–RGD had better target-to-background signals than the unattached RGDC and saline groups, implying that modified-RGDC improved PDA PA imaging efficiency. Furthermore, PDA–RGD/DOX nanoparticles demonstrated significant photothermal effectiveness, tumor tissue accumulation, and excellent biocompatibility and biodegradability. A nanoplatform like this might be useful for cancer treatment that is guided by PA imaging in the clinic. The precise interaction of RGD and α_3 integrin slows tumor development and begins the apoptotic process, in addition to its capacity to target malignancies. PDA films were coated on Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles in a second work, and NH₂–PEG–cRGD was connected to them. (45) The multifunctional nanoparticle was effective in targeting tumors in vivo, according to experiments.

2.3.2 Nuclear-Targeted Peptide (TAT)

Unlike prior reports of polydopamine-covered nanomaterial surfaces, a PDA–MSN composite nanoparticle was made via self-assembly synthesis followed by TAT grafting (46). Polydopamine and silica blocks were bonded utilizing amino/thiol group-containing silanes throughout the production process, and DOX was loaded via a host–guest interaction. Finally, for nuclear targeting, TAT–SH, a nuclear-targeting peptide modified with a mercapto group, was added to its surface. The targeting was confirmed using confocal laser scanning microscopy. TAT-modified M–PDA–MSN nanoparticles were discovered mostly in the nuclear area of MCF-7/ADR cells, with no modified-TAT nanoparticles discovered in the cytoplasm, showing that TAT-modification was able to increase nanoparticle entrance into MCF-7/ADR cells and subsequently target the nucleus. In MCF-7 cells, TAT@M–PDA–MSN nanoparticles showed more apparent inhibitory efficacy and a higher level of apoptosis than the other groups. However, no animal studies were undertaken in this work, and further research into the therapeutic potential of such nanoparticles for cancer treatments is needed.

3. Monotherapy Polydopamine Nanoparticles

3.1 Photothermal Therapy

PTT, which uses nanomaterials with high photothermal conversion efficiency to create heat for tumor ablation using NIR irradiation, has become popular because of its low risk of damaging healthy tissues and its great efficiency. PTT-capable photothermal materials have been identified, including Au, carbon-based materials, Cu-based semiconductors, and indocyanine green. (47-49) Because of their robust biocompatibility, good photothermal conversion efficiency, and biodegradability, PDA-based systems have been widely employed for PTT. The photothermal characteristics of dopamine nanospheres (160 nm) for tumor therapy were investigated by Lu and colleagues (50). They started by looking at their UV-vis absorption spectra, which revealed that PDA had obvious absorption in the NIR spectrum. PDA at various concentrations was compared to pure water after 500 seconds of irradiation at 808 nm to investigate its photothermal conversion efficiency. The temperature of the polydopamine solution rapidly rose as the time of irradiation increased. Furthermore, the rate of temperature rise was faster at higher PDA concentrations. The temperature of the polydopamine solution (200 g mL⁻¹) climbed to 33.6 °C after 500 seconds of irradiation, but pure water only climbed to 3.2 °C. Finally, the therapeutic potential was tested in mice with 4T1 tumors *in vivo*. Following irradiation with an 808 nm laser, the materials containing PDA more effectively ablated tumors than the other groups, with no tumor recurrence or harm to healthy tissue after 10 days. Finally, polydopamine demonstrated excellent NIR absorption and excellent light-to-heat conversion efficiency, resulting in effective tumor ablation and tumor growth suppression with minimal adverse effects.

3.2 Chemotherapy

PDA NPs can be used as drug-loaded nanocarriers for chemotherapy in addition to photothermal treatment. PDA NPs have been studied extensively for use in chemotherapeutic applications, with several research published. 51 and 52 (Long-term blood circulation of nanocarriers based on PDA is still a problem. Wang et al. (53) used stacking to create lollipop-like dual-drug-loaded nanoparticles, dubbed DOX-PDA-gossypol NPs, in order to circumvent drug resistance and quick elimination *in vivo*. With pH-dependent drug release, the drug loading index of the NPs (59.6 9.6 nm in diameter) was determined to be 91 percent. They discovered that the NPs stayed in the blood circulation for an extremely long time (>192 hours), and that their elimination half-life was 458 times longer than that of free DOX. The results *in vivo* showed that the NPs have outstanding anticancer activities with little toxicity, indicating that they have a lot of potential for cancer treatment.

3.3 Immunotherapy

By using Michael addition, adjuvants containing amine and thiol groups may easily connect to the catechol groups on PDA NPs, allowing PDA NPs to load a large number of adjuvant molecules. A PDA that has not been changed has high biocompatibility and can control DC maturation. (54) As a result, PDA NPs might be used as adjuvant nanocarriers in immunotherapy. Wang et al. (54) grafted the antigen ovalbumin (OVA) onto PDA NPs to improve their effectiveness as adjuvant delivery vehicles. The PDA loaded with OVA had a loading capacity of 754 g mg⁻¹, which was much higher than other nanoparticles, suggesting that PDA NPs had a high antigen loading capacity. OVA@PDA-NPs showed essentially little biological toxicity in cytotoxicity and cellular uptake experiments, and were swallowed in larger numbers by bone marrow-derived dendritic cells (BMDCs) (98.2 percent 0.4 percent) than NPs in the free OVA group (76.2 percent 2.9 percent). DCs are well-known for their importance in immunotherapy. After treatment with OVA@PDA-NPs, the expression of DC maturity markers increased, indicating that they had matured. A colon cancer-bearing mouse

model was used to test their anticancer capabilities. Mice given OVA@PDA-NPs had a lower tumor volume than mice given other treatments, and cytotoxic CD8⁺ T-cells specific for cancer immunotherapy-OVA were observed to be activated. As a consequence, the vaccine vector OVA@PdopNPs has the potential to be used in cancer immunotherapy. Similarly, Leng et al. (56) used tumor cell lysate (TCL) to connect to PDA NPs to create a stable cancer therapeutic vaccination for colorectal cancer. TCL was more convenient than other peptide vaccinations since it did not need antigenic identification. They looked at BMDC maturation, immune cell activation, memory T-cell response, and tumor progression to see how it affected them. TCL@PDA NPs showed long-term anticancer characteristics in the animal model, owing to a reduction in immunosuppression-related cells and the activation of CD4⁺, CD8⁺, and memory T-cells in tumor tissues. These findings show that polydopamine nanoparticles may be used as vaccine nanocarriers in cancer immunotherapy to transport adjuvants such as mRNA, DNA, or synthetic long peptides. PDA-NP-based cancer vaccines are attractive options for therapeutic cancer treatment due to their low toxicity, facile production, and immunostimulatory activity.

4. Multifunctional Platforms Based on Polydopamine for Synergistic Therapy

Because of their exceptional photothermal conversion efficiency and great biocompatibility, polydopamine-based multifunctional delivery systems have been explored for synergistic cancer treatment. However, because of the uneven heat distribution and the intricacy of tumors, a single photothermal therapy with PDA is insufficient to eradicate a tumor and can potentially result in tumor recurrence or metastasis. PDA can be used to build a multifunctional platform with which to combine different therapies, such as combined PTT/chemotherapy, PTT/radiotherapy, PTT/chemo-/gene therapy, or PTT/immune therapy, enhancing antitumor efficacy and reducing side effects, thanks to its ease of functionalization with other nanomaterials.

4.1 PTT/Chemotherapy

Monotherapy, such as PTT or chemotherapy, has drawbacks, such as unequal heat distribution in PTT (57) and chemotherapy's nonspecific distribution and multidrug resistance. (58) Polydopamine has greater drug-carrying capacity due to the catechol and amino groups, which can be used in chemo-photothermal combination treatment. To address the limitations of in situ drug release, Li et al. (59) developed a PDA-based carrier-free nanoparticle with NIR- and pH-responsiveness that can release cancer medicines. DOX, a hydrophobic chemotherapeutic drug, was reprecipitated into carrier-free DOX nanoparticles (DNPs) and subsequently bundled with NH₄HCO₃ into a PDA film to extend its circulation inside the bloodstream. The drug loading efficiency of DNPs/N@PDA was found to be as high as 85.8%. The PDA film created a significant amount of heat when subjected to NIR laser irradiation, thereby prompting NH₄HCO₃ to decompose into carbon dioxide and ammonia gas, resulting in a "bomb-like" in situ "bomb-like" release of DOX. They looked into the drug's release further and discovered that, depending on the environmental circumstances, the nanoparticle undergoing drug release was pH- and NIR-responsive. When treated with DNPs/N@PDA and irradiated with NIR at pH 5.0, the group treated with DNPs/N@PDA produced 1.6-fold more DOX and had greater therapeutic efficacy than the group treated with DNPs, showing greater synergistic chemo/photothermal therapeutic efficacy. In addition to serving as a drug carrier, polydopamine can be used to coat a variety of nanomaterials, including metal nanoparticles (60) and mesoporous silicon nanoparticles (61), with the goal of preventing drug leakage, controlling drug release, and providing a superior photothermal effect on nanoplatfoms. Polydopamine was coated on the surface of

DOX-loaded mesoporous silica nanoparticles to provide a unique biocompatible drug delivery system with different sensitivities. (62) The PDA, in addition to acting as a photothermal treatment agent, was discovered to operate as a gatekeeper, regulating medication release. It facilitated the release of the medication that prevented tumor development when activated by pH or NIR irradiation, while polydopamine transformed photonic radiation into heat to destroy cancer cells.

Drug resistance remains an issue, despite the fact that chemotherapy coupled with photothermal treatment can enhance treatment results. It has been established that by combining two drugs with distinct antitumor mechanisms, drug resistance can be overcome. (64, 63) Li et al. (65) developed a drug-loaded nanoplatfrom based on PDA and zeolitic imidazolate framework-8 (ZIF-8) nanoparticles to provide photothermal treatment and chemotherapy in concert. PDA was used as a photothermal agent and a secondary modification platform to introduce heptakis-(6-mercapto-6-deoxy)-cyclodextrin in this application (CDs). For dual drug loading, ZIF-8 was modified with PDA, which added CDs to the PDA domains. The CDs contain a hydrophobic drug (hydroxycamptothecin), while the hollow-cavity ZIF-8 has a hydrophilic drug (DOX). The treatment results showed that the multifunctional nanoplatforms had more efficacious chemo-photothermal effects than the other groups, both in vitro and in vivo.

Gao and colleagues developed a PDA-based system for dual medication loading and active tumor targeting in another investigation. (66) The anticancer medication docetaxel, which is hydrophobic, was enclosed in polymeric nanoparticles and subsequently coated with PDA. Following that, DOX and PEG-modified AS1411 were loaded onto PDA film by stacking and a Michael addition reaction. To summarize, the photothermal efficiency of PDA nanoplatforms with pH and NIR-responsive drug release behavior was exceptional. The nanoplatform was selectively targeted and enriched in MCF-7 human breast cancer cells, significantly increasing the photothermal impact, increasing drug bioavailability, and minimizing the risk of harm to healthy cells.

4.2 Photodynamic Therapy (PTT)

The combination of photodynamic treatment (PDT) and photothermal treatment (PTT) has a lot of potential for improving treatment results and overcoming issues, including uneven heat distribution and hypoxic conditions in tumor cells. PDA is frequently utilized in PDT/PTT combination therapy due to its high photothermal conversion and ubiquitous surface modification capacity. Photosensitizers can stay in the bloodstream for longer when combined with polydopamine, as previously demonstrated. (67) However, the hypoxic environment of solid tumors continues to restrict the efficacy of PDT-based combination treatment, resulting in partial tumor eradication and even metastasis. (68) Fortunately, catalase can process excess H₂O₂ created by tumor cells to create oxygen. To alleviate hypoxia, Feng and colleagues (69) added oxygen-producing enzymes to the surface of PDA. A multifunctional ZIF-8-gated PDA nanoparticle was created by adding photosensitizer and catalase (CAT) onto the surface of PDA, achieving simultaneous photodynamic and photothermal treatment. The findings showed that CAT-mediated self-sufficient O₂ production offered excellent PDT treatment, and that the multimode treatment system was more successful than monotherapy in eradicating malignancies. Catalase, on the other hand, is restricted by its instability in circulation. (70) For the creation of oxygen, a number of stable oxygen-generating metal complexes, such as manganese dioxide (MnO₂), can be used instead of catalase. For synergistic breast cancer therapy, Zeng et al. (21) used hollow mesoporous MnO₂ as a core,

which was loaded with the photosensitizer chlorin e6 (Ce6), then coated with PDA film to introduce a targeting agent (folic acid). Due to the catalytic activity of MnO₂, it was discovered that endogenous H₂O₂ continued to create huge amounts of oxygen. In a mouse model, NPs accumulated at tumor sites due to active targeting by folic acid, resulting in a precise antitumor effect. Ce6 was particularly produced when exposed to a mild acid environment or external near-infrared light stimulation due to the presence of PDA, decreasing harmful side effects and improving therapeutic success. In vitro and in vivo research revealed that the cooperative oxygen-elevating and combination thermal treatment (PDT/PTT) had stronger anticancer activity than PTT or PDT alone.

Transporting oxygen to the location of a tumor has been investigated as an alternative to creating oxygen in situ. Liu et al. (22) (72) created invasive artificial red blood cells (AmmRBC) to ameliorate the hypoxic environment and boost photodynamic treatment, based on red blood cells in mammals that can provide oxygen. They coupled hemoglobin with an enzyme-mimicking PDA that was loaded with photosensitizer at the same time, and then used a recombinant RBC membrane to enclose the nanoparticles' surface. PDA acts similarly to antioxidant enzymes in RBCs in this system, shielding hemoglobin from oxidative destruction during systemic circulation, in addition to creating a photothermal impact. The AmmRBCs were effective in enriching the site of the tumor area and enhancing the tumor's hypoxic microenvironment, thereby enhancing the PTT-PDT combined therapy. Although the harsh synthetic environment will restrict its applicability, this artificial erythrocyte camouflage approach may be employed as an effective platform to ameliorate hypoxia.

PDT without oxygen, rather than directly supplying oxygen, is a helpful approach to combating tumor hypoxia. The Fenton reaction ($\text{Fe}^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{3+} + \text{OH}^- + \cdot\text{OH}$), which is not dependent on oxygen, can produce the most poisonous reactive oxygen species, causing cancer cells to die. (73) First, a platinum-PDA hybrid nanocomposite was created, to which cyclodextrin (CD) groups on the PDA surface were linked. Finally, PDA-Pt-CD@RuFc nanoparticles were formed by loading a Ru (II) complex (RuFc) onto the CD via a host-guest interaction. The RuFc was released under any of the conditions: mild acidity, near-infrared heating, or H₂O₂. The platinum NPs stimulated the conversion of H₂O₂ to O₂ via a photocatalytic Fenton reaction, with RuFc generating $\cdot\text{OH}$. PDA was able to create heat, cause vasodilation to relieve hypoxia, create thermography, and harm cancer cells as a photothermal and photothermal imaging agent. PDA-Pt-CD@RuFc also has strong imaging capabilities, such as PA and computed tomography (CT) imaging, allowing diagnosis and therapy to be combined. Finally, mice with 4T1 tumors were employed to test the combo therapy's anticancer effectiveness. After 14 days of therapy, tumors in mice injected with PDA-Pt-CD@RuFc were nearly completely gone, whereas PDT or PTT alone only showed modest tumor suppression. To summarize, nanoparticles have promise for integrating PDT/PTT treatment with diagnostics using photothermal, PA, or CT imaging, and they can help advance precision medicine.

4.3 PTT/Radiation Therapy

Radiation therapy (RT) is a conventional anticancer technique that uses X-ray or γ -ray radiation to kill cancer cells by destroying their DNA or releasing hazardous oxygen radicals. (76) The substantial adverse effects and poor therapeutic effectiveness produced by tissue hypoxia limit the use of mono-radiation treatment. (77) Following NIR light irradiation, local hyperthermia therapy increases blood flow, bringing more oxygen to the tumor. (78) The combination of radiation and photothermal treatment has sparked a lot of studies in order to

improve the therapeutic impact and reduce tissue damage. To accomplish the combination of radioisotope treatment and PTT, PDA might be used to administer radionuclides or photothermal agents. (79)

To accomplish this, a radiosensitizer (WS2 QDs) was inserted within a mesoporous polydopamine (MPDA) nanoparticle. Finally, they added manganese dioxide to the mix (MnO₂). (80) To test the nanoparticles' heating impact in vivo, 4T1 tumor-bearing mice were injected with nanoparticles and then irradiated with 808 nm NIR laser light (1.5 W cm²) for 5 minutes over the tumor site after 12 hours. They discovered that animals treated with MPDA–WS2@MnO₂ NPs produced thermal energy within tumor tissue, reaching temperatures of 54 °C in 4 minutes, which was sufficient to destroy cancer cells. The resulting nanocomposite enhanced radiotherapy while also attaining a much higher PDT–PTT combo treatment. There was no evident weight loss in any of the mice, showing that the MPDA–WS2@MnO₂ NPs were biocompatible. In contrast to conventional drug delivery systems that provide short-term oxygenation, You and colleagues (81) formed O₂-PIr@Si@PDA, a long-term oxygen storage nanoplatfrom to improve anticancer treatment by combining RI and PTT treatment. They used perfluorooctyl bromide (PFOB) as an oxygen storage material, along with an oxygen-sensitive probe (Ir (I)) that shone and became attached to PFOB when exposed to oxygen. To enable photothermal treatment and regulated drug release, it was finally encased in silica and covered with polydopamine. The nanosystem was able to store oxygen for more than 7 days thanks to the silicon shell. By cracking the silicon shell, the medication was released in a temperature-responsive manner. At the same time, the Ir (I) complex detected oxygen emission in the presence of light. The findings showed that maintaining an aerobic microenvironment slowed tumor development and improved the therapeutic efficacy of nasopharyngeal cancer treatment.

4.4 PTT/Gene Therapy

Small interfering RNAs (siRNA), for example, are able to influence the expression of particular genes and proteins in cancer cells, causing them to die. So far, siRNA has been used in both single-agent and multi-agent anticancer treatments. The efficient integration of controlled gene therapy with the administration of photothermal agents remains a difficulty, despite the fact that PTT/gene combination therapy has been shown to have a great anticancer impact. (82) Wang et al. (83) devised a siRNA delivery technique for cooperative PTT and gene therapy utilizing hybrid MPDA and calcium phosphate (CaP). To improve the loading of siRNA molecules, the surface of MPDA was decorated with tertiary amines, and subsequently coated with CaP by biomineralization to avoid premature release. The controlled-release capacity of MPDA–siRNA@CaP was tested using polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis. At pH 5, siRNA was released, but none was released at pH 7.4, indicating that the CaP coating was degraded within the tumor microenvironment. In addition, a fluorescence-labeled colocalization investigation was carried out in Hep-G2 cells to assess MPDA–siRNA@CaP endosomal escape. Green fluorescence from SYBR Green I labeled MPDA–siRNA@CaP was identified intracellularly, but no colocalization with LysoTracker Red-tagged lysosomes was identified, suggesting that the MPDA @ CaP helped avoid the proton sponge effect's capture of lysosomes. Finally, they looked at the therapeutic outcomes of MPDA–siRNA@CaP delivery, finding that it resulted in significant tumor eradication and greater therapeutic efficiency than monotherapy.

In addition to the aforementioned, the problem of local inflammation and tumor spreading induced by high temperatures (over 50 °C) following photothermal treatment is being

investigated in conjunction with gene therapy. As a result, developing a successful low-temperature photothermal treatment is critical. A PDA-coated nucleic acid nanogel was devised to solve this problem, (84), permitting siRNA-mediated low-temperature PTT. To make siRNA-embedded nanogels, researchers crossed anti-Hsp70 siRNA with DNA-grafted polycaprolactone (DNA-g-PCL), which inhibits Hsp70 production. These were then coated with PDA to prevent enzymatic breakdown and achieve high photothermal conversion efficiency. Finally, polyethylene glycol was added to create long-term circulation in vivo. The researchers initially looked at the absorption of PDA-coated nucleic acid nanogels (PEG–PDA–Nanogel) by HeLa cells and the effect of gene silencing. They discovered that the PEG–PDA–Nanogel was well absorbed. Furthermore, the PEG–PDA–Nanogel was more effective than the nanogel alone at suppressing the production of heat shock proteins in HeLa cells under near-infrared laser irradiation, effectively killing tumor cells in low-temperature settings. Finally, a tumor-bearing nude mouse model was created to test the pharmacokinetic characteristics and anticancer effects of low-temperature photothermal therapy. In vivo, PEG–PDA–Nanogel had a longer circulation period, increased tumor enrichment, and suppressed tumor development at low temperatures to a larger extent than the other groups.

4.5 PTT/Chemotherapy/Gene Therapy

A multifunctional codelivery system based on PDA and black phosphorus (BP) nanosheets (NSs) was devised for targeted chemo, gene, and PTT treatment to improve antitumor efficacy even further. (85) Multidrug resistance (MDR) is regulated by permeability glycoprotein (P-gp), and P-gp siRNA has been shown to diminish P-gp expression and hence overcome MDR. (86) P-gp siRNA and DOX were first loaded onto the black phosphorus, followed by P-gp siRNA and DOX. For enhanced stability, PDA was given to the BP NSs, which were then modified using NH₂–PEG–Apt. When subjected to NIR irradiation, the BP–PDA therapeutic platform showed a greater temperature increase, suggesting that BP coupled with PDA increased the photothermal effectiveness of BP NSs. The drug release performance was investigated, and the findings revealed that DOX release was influenced by pH and photo-dependent behavior. Furthermore, studies of cellular absorption and cellular targeting revealed that this new nanocarrier targeted tumor cells preferentially. P-gp expression and tumor growth were suppressed best in the BP-R-D@PDAPEG-Apt + NIR group, demonstrating that synergistic chemo-, gene-, and PTT treatment was accomplished.

4.6 Immunotherapy/PTT

Cancer immunotherapy is now seen to be the most promising treatment for cancer, as it controls and eliminates tumors by triggering a natural antitumor immune response. (87) Photothermal treatment promotes tumor cell death, which releases tumor-specific antigens, triggering a systemic immunological response, including DC and CD8⁺ T cell activation. (88) A lot of publications have been published on combined PTT/immunotherapy employing PDA for cancer therapy. Nam et al. created PDA-coated spiky gold nanoparticles loaded with DOX to show that combining PTT with chemotherapy may trigger powerful antitumor immunity. (89) They discovered that covering the spiky gold nanoparticles with PDA not only made them more stable, but also improved their photothermal impact. DOX boosted immunological activation induced by PTT, which was validated. Surprisingly, PTT elicited a significant systemic immune response, including the elicitation of anticancer CD8⁺ T-cells and NK cells, as well as the eradication of local and untreated distant CT26 colon cancer in >85% of mice. A very aggressive advanced cancer model was also developed to evaluate the treatment efficacy of cancer spread and recurrence. As a result, nanoparticles significantly slow the development of untreated distant tumors. Overall, the use of polydopamine-coated spiky gold

nanoparticles loaded with DOX in chemo-photothermal treatment has revealed novel elements of immunology and advanced cancer therapy.

Polydopamine also mixes with materials that can act as immune agents to improve immunotherapy, in addition to activating an immune response utilizing photothermal treatment. M2 macrophages provide an immunosuppressive milieu, which is a common concern in cancer treatment. Iron chelation has been created to repolarize macrophages toward an M1 phenotype rather than an M2 phenotype, allowing T-helper and effector T-cells to destroy cancer cells. For M2-to-M1 TAM repolarization and photothermal treatment, PDA-iron chelating nanomaterials (Fe@PDA-PEG) were created. (90) Because of the catechol groups on PDA, the nanoparticles had a high Fe³⁺ chelation capacity after being coated with PEGylated polydopamine, as well as strong photothermal effectiveness. The findings revealed that following photothermal therapy, cancer cells perished, and tumor-associated antigens (TAAs) were released via the major histocompatibility complex class II (MHC II) route, activating a T-cell-dependent antitumor response. Fe@PDA-PEG polarized M2 TAMs into an M1 phenotype, according to experiments. TAA presentation and effector T-cell infiltration helped to alter the immunosuppressive tumor microenvironment, inhibiting tumor development and malignant metastasis. Flow cytometry was used to investigate the antitumor immune response. In the Fe@PDA-PEG+NIR treatment group, the fraction of M2-like macrophages (CD206^{high}) decreased, indicating that the nanoparticles had the capacity to drive the polarization of M2 TAMs into an M1 phenotype. In addition, the number of T-helper cells (CD3⁺ CD4⁺) and cytotoxic T lymphocytes (CD3⁺ CD8⁺) in tumor sites rose dramatically. Finally, tumors shrank in both a subcutaneous colon tumor model and an orthotopic breast cancer model, and mice survived longer. Iron oxide NPs (Fe₃O₄@PDA), which include a Fe₃O₄ core and a PDA film, have also been created for the treatment of nonsmall cell lung cancer. (91)

The Fe₃O₄ core not only permitted imaging, but it also allowed the tumor to be magnetically targeted. In the fight against cancer, NK cells, an immune cell that is involved in the detection and removal of cancer cells as well as the suppression of metastasis, play a critical role. The ability of NK cells to consume iron oxide NPs in a dose-dependent way has been established, as demonstrated in the experiment.

Fe₃O₄@PDA NPs (50 g mL⁻¹) were incubated with NK cells for 12 hours before TEM analysis, which revealed that Fe₃O₄@PDA NPs were taken up by NK cells at a higher rate than Fe₃O₄, showing that PDA increases cellular absorption. To maximize the recruitment of NK cells, a small external magnetic device was placed near the tumor. The findings showed that NK cells in the Fe₃O₄@PDA NPs group aggregated more near the tumor site due to the magnetic traction effect of the NPs, resulting in stronger tumor inhibition than those in the control groups.

Immune therapies that produce significant suppression of in situ or metastatic cancers, including monoclonal antibody-type immune checkpoint inhibitors, therapeutic antibodies, cancer vaccines, and small molecule inhibitors, can be coupled with PDA for synthetic PTT/immune treatment. (92-95) Chen et al. (96) used dopamine oxidation and self-polymerization to make Al₂O₃ nanoparticles modified with PDA. As indicated by the long-term usage of aluminum compound microparticles (such as alum) in human vaccinations, Al₂O₃ nanoparticles can be employed as an immunological adjuvant. Prior to irradiation with near-infrared laser light for PTT, pD-Al₂O₃ nanoparticles were administered into tumors

rather than intravenously to prevent first-pass hepatic metabolism. Photothermography revealed a temperature increase of up to 55.0 °C in 5 minutes, indicating that the pD–Al₂O₃ nanoparticles had a good photothermal impact. Large-scale tumor cell killing was triggered by the local intratumoral temperature. The Al₂O₃ nanoparticles and the release of tumor-specific antigens triggered an immune response that wiped out any remaining tumor. CpG, an immunological adjuvant that activates Th1-type cells, was administered to the mice on days 1, 3, and 5 to boost the antitumor immune response. Notably, CD40+ or CD86+ expression was significantly higher in the PTT (pD–Al₂O₃ nanoparticles) combined with immunotherapy (CpG) group, suggesting that PTT (pD–Al₂O₃ nanoparticles) combined with immunotherapy (CpG) triggered dendritic cell maturation and ultimately an improved antitumor immune response. Furthermore, the mice treated with the combination treatment lived 4–10 times longer than the other groups, demonstrating that PPT based on PDA paired with adjuvant compounds does actually improve immunotherapy. The metabolism of Al₂O₃ nanoparticles in humans, on the other hand, can have harmful consequences and poses an unknown danger. Because they are non-excludable, toll-like receptor (TLR) agonists are a promising adjuvant for anticancer immunotherapy. By loading TLR 7 agonists inside MPDA nanocarriers, Lu et al. (97) created a composite nanoparticle. The surface of the composite nanoparticles was changed to polyvinyl pyrrolidone to guarantee that the TLR agonists went exactly to the lymphatic tissues. The nanoparticles were discovered to be responsible for DC maturation. Additionally, after photothermal therapy, the immune response has increased even more, inhibiting the formation of subcutaneous B16 melanomas.

PDA collaborates with the immune blockade inhibitor PD-L1 to produce cooperative phototherapy and immunotherapy for treating malignancies, in addition to enabling immunological adjuvants. A PD-L1 (programmed cell death ligand 1) blocker has been utilized in cancer immunotherapy with promising outcomes. (98) JQ1, a PD-L1 inhibitor that inhibits c-MYC transcription, is a bromodomain and extra-terminal (BET) inhibitor.

Tian et al. (1999) created a JQ1-loaded polydopamine nanoparticle (PDMN-JQ1) as a compact nanoplatform to accomplish the synergy of immunotherapy, PTT, and c-MYC-targeting to treat triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC). This was the first study to look at the interaction between a BET inhibitor and PTT. The loading efficiency of PDMN was as high as 23.3 percent in drug loading and release research, with JQ1 release recorded for two weeks in a simulated tumor microenvironment. The temperature of PDMN-JQ1 increased dramatically by 25 °C after being exposed to near infrared light for 300 seconds, indicating that PDMN and PDMN-JQ1 have remarkable photothermal effects. Western blot examination revealed that following treatment with PDMN-JQ1, the expression levels of c-MYC and PD-L1 in 4T1 cells were significantly lowered, confirming that it repressed the expression of c-MYC and PD-L1. In the end, the anticancer impact was investigated in vivo. PDMN-JQ1 was injected intramuscularly to optimize the efficiency of administration and to reduce any systemic harmful side effects. The study found that following cell ablation, intracellular tumor-associated antigens are released, and JQ1 causes a reduction in PD-L1 expression, resulting in a powerful immune response and activation of powerful immunological memory T cells, which protect against TNBC recurrence. Furthermore, the development of both main and distant tumors was clearly suppressed with minimal systemic adverse effects, showing that PDA NSs-based delivery methods paired with a BET inhibitor might be used in clinical trials in the future.

4.7 PTT/PDT/Immunotherapy

Synergistic phototherapy based on PDT and PTT has been shown to be successful in combating tumor heterogeneity and complexity. Previous techniques, on the other hand, were only relevant to in-situ cancers, neglecting cancer spread. 100 and 101 (Yan and colleagues described a combination PDT/PTT employing PDA and chlorin e6 (Ce6) that synergized with immune checkpoint blockade of PD-1 to reduce tumor recurrence and metastasis. (102) The procedure was as follows: coprecipitation production of PDA nanoparticles, hydrothermal coating with a NaGdF₄:Yb/Er shell, and lastly, loading Ce6 on the outermost layer. Both PTT and PDT cause immunogenic cells to be destroyed and an immunological response to be triggered. PDT also caused tumor cells to express higher amounts of calreticulin, which served as a "eat-me" signal for dendritic cells to consume, triggering an antitumor immune response. This dual-modal phototherapy efficiently facilitated dendritic cell maturation, activated CD8⁺ cytotoxic T lymphocytes (CTL), attracted other immunocytes, such as macrophages and B-cells, and suppressed tumor development, as predicted, following irradiation with 980 nm NIR light. Activation of CTLs is mostly restricted by immunological checkpoints, despite the fact that cooperative phototherapy can initiate an anticancer immune response.

As a result, PDA@UCNP/Ce6 in combination with a PD-1 inhibitor was tested for tumor metastasis inhibition. Tumors of type 4T1 were treated. PDA@UCNP/Ce6 in combination with a PD-1 inhibitor was beneficial in preventing tumor spreading and extending mouse lifespan, but basic phototherapy was ineffective. To summarize, this work reported a unique kind of immunotherapy for cancer metastasis that included cooperative phototherapy and a PD-1 blocking antibody, which might have major implications for the development of immune antitumor therapy.

4.8 Other Synergistic Therapies

4.8.1 PTT/Biotherapy

Polydopamine is a possible nanomaterial for biological treatment since dopamine, the basic material used to make polydopamine, is also distributed among people. Salmonella VNP20009, a facultative anaerobe, may thrive in the hypoxic environment of a tumor. However, due to limited tumor treatment effects and dose-related toxicity and side effects, the first phase of the clinical trial of VNP20009 was halted. Chen and co-workers (103) devised an approach to enhance melanoma treatment results by combining the benefits of VNP20009 with the benefits of polydopamine's photothermal treatment. Using oxidative self-polymerization, polydopamine was added to VNP20009. Polydopamine-coated VNP20009 proved successful in targeting the hypoxic zone of solid tumors after injection into the tail vein. When bombarded with near-infrared light, the temperature of the tumor tissue increases. The malignancies were fully ablated with no recurrence or metastasis after this combined treatment. VNP20009 and polydopamine, in particular, showed promising anticancer properties.

4.8.2 PTT/Gas Therapy

Due to their lack of side effects and favorable treatment results, gaseous molecules such as NO, H₂, H₂S, and CO have been identified as viable candidates for anticancer treatment. Polydopamine mesopores were produced to load MnCO for CO treatment and PTT. (104) MnCO was found to react with tumor-enriched H₂O₂ and create CO gas in situ to kill cancer cells when the nanoparticles reached the size of the tumor. Meanwhile, the Mn²⁺ created during the procedure might be used as a magnetic resonance imaging contrast agent (MRI). Finally, both in vitro and in vivo investigations revealed that CO and PTT working together

killed tumors and reduced their recurrence. PDA in conjunction with gaseous molecules, we believe, will be the focus of more in-depth research in the future.

5. Conclusion

Finally, this review has comprehensively assessed new PDA research investigations, including targeted treatment and cancer synergistic medicines. We've compiled a list of the many sorts of PDA-based multifunctional platforms for enhanced synergistic medicines. Recent advances in photothermal treatment paired with sophisticated treatments, such as gene therapy, radiation, and notably immunotherapy, have been emphasized. Due to its superior biocompatibility, degradability, low toxicity, and high photothermal conversion efficiency, PDA may be produced by easy oxidative self-polymerization of dopamine and serve as an ideal nanocarrier or photothermal agent for cancer therapy. More significantly, due to its high adhesive capabilities, PDA may readily be functionalized with a variety of nanomaterials for synergistic cancer treatment, in addition to its superior photothermal effects.

Although PDA-based multifunctional nanoplatfoms for synergistic cancer therapy, such as chemo-photothermal treatment and photodynamic–photothermal treatment, have received a lot of attention, finding new uses for PDA remains difficult. First, despite its easy and mild synthesis procedure, large-scale synthesis with uniform size and thickness is difficult due to a lack of consistent quality control standards. Second, due to PDA's high adhesive capabilities, multifunctional nanoplatfoms functionalized with it are likely to agglomerate in the solution. Third, in order to enhance PDA's clinical use, its safety should be thoroughly investigated. However, before being used in clinical settings, PDA-based multifunctional systems need more investigation. A PDA-based multifunctional platform for improved synergistic cancer therapy is a promising approach for the future. PDA-based systems used in immunotherapy, in particular, will continue to be a research hotspot.

In addition to immunotherapy, the integration of cancer diagnosis and treatment has gotten a lot of press in recent years. Polyphenols have been shown to prevent tumor growth and to interact with metals such as Fe^{3+} , Pt^{4+} , Cu^{2+} , and others to create metal-phenolic networks (MPNs). MPNs are biocompatible, functionalizable, pH-responsive, and have the potential to escape endosomes. (105, 106) PDA has the potential to form MPNs with magnetic resonance contrast agents, such as gadolinium, due to the vast number of catechol groups on its surface, permitting magnetic resonance imaging. Polyphenols also have a tumor-inhibiting impact, and the photothermal action of PDA can ablate tumors. As a result, PDA-based MPNs might be a viable avenue for integrating diagnosis and therapy.

In addition, polydopamine can crosslink with acrylamide and other polymers to generate anticancer and antibacterial hydrogels. (107) Increasing the stickiness of polydopamine hydrogels is currently in progress, paving the way for the creation of self-adhesive hydrogel bioelectronics. Bioelectron self-adhesion and other functionalities, such as self-healing, transparency, and bacterio-toxicity, might be given to polydopamine hydrogels by modulating the redox mechanism of phenolquinone. A potential development trend is the incorporation of self-adhesive hydrogels into already existing bioelectronic materials. Polydopamine hydrogels will eventually evolve from skin patches to implantable integrated bioelectronics (108-170).

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